

Proton Ligand Formation Constants of 4-Hydroxy-5-Carboxy-4'-Methoxy-Azo-Benzene and Formation Constants of Its Complexes with Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II)

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The proton-ligand formation constants of 4-hydroxy-5-carboxy-4'-methoxy-azo-benzene and formation constants of its complexes with Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) have been determined by various computational methods. The order of stability (of $\log K_1$) is found to be Cu(II) > Zn(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II). The results indicate chelation through 4-hydroxy and 5-carboxy groups of the salicylic residue.

AZO-DYES have been reported to form coloured complexes with a number of metal cations¹⁻⁵. The present paper deals with the complex forming tendency of the azo-dye derived from salicylic acid and *p*-anisidine. Approximate values of the proton-ligand formation constants of the ligand and the formation constants of its complexes with Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) were obtained in ethanol-water mixture (75% vol/vol) at 20° from the half-integral values employing pH-titration technique⁶⁻⁷. Refined values were then obtained by pointwise calculations and linear plot methods.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of either B.D.H. (AnalaR) or equivalent quality. The metal salt-solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Since the ligand is insoluble in water, its solution was prepared in ethanol-water (75% vol/vol). pH of the solutions were measured using Polymetron CL-41 pH meter. The measurements were made with an

accuracy of ± 0.05 pH unit and the reproducibility of the readings was of the same order. The experimental set up, procedure and methods of calculations are the same as described earlier⁸⁻¹⁰.

Solutions containing ligand, perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate were titrated with standard NaOH. After the addition of each portion of NaOH solution, the B value, i.e., pH meter reading, in mixed solvent was noted. Similar titrations were then performed with the metal salt in the reaction mixture and also in the absence of the ligand.

Results and Discussion

The values of $\log K^H_1$ and $\log K^H_2$ corresponding to the association of the two protons in 4-hydroxy-5-carboxy-4'-methoxy-azo-benzene have been calculated by half-integral, pointwise calculations and also by the linear plot of B versus $\log \bar{n}H/1-\bar{n}H$ at each point in the region where $\bar{n}H$ is 2-1 and 1-0 respectively and are recorded in Table 1. The

TABLE 1: PROTON-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF METAL CHELATES OF 4-HYDROXY-5-CARBOXY-4'-METHOXY-AZO-BENZENE

	Log K_1				log K_2			
	H	L	P	A	H	L	P	A
	M E T H O D S *							
H ⁺	10.12	—	10.12	10.12	3.40	3.40	3.41	3.40
Cu(II)	8.85	8.85	8.92	8.87	6.05	6.05	6.11	6.07
Zn(II)	6.70	6.65	6.75	6.70				
Ni(II)	6.70	6.70	6.61	6.67				
Co(II)	6.45	6.45	6.52	6.47				

*H = Half integral method
L = Linear plot method
P = Pointwise calculations method
A = Average value

reaction indicates that $\log K^H_1$ and $\log K^H_2$ corresponds to the association of proton to 4-hydroxy and 5-carboxy groups respectively. This is in accordance with earlier results^{11,12}.

A series of values of $\bar{n}$ and $p(L)$ corresponding to different values of B were calculated and formation curves were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ against $p(L)$.

Only in case of copper the values of $\bar{n}$ exceed 1.5 showing the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. In case of Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) the values of $\bar{n}$ never exceed 0.9 showing thereby that these metal ions form only 1 : 1 complexes in solution under the experimental conditions used. The values of $\log K_1$ and also $\log K_2$ in case of copper were directly read from the formation curves employing the half integral values of $\bar{n}$ as described by Bjerrum and are recorded in Table 1. The refined values of $\log K_1$ and also $\log K_2$ in case of copper are then obtained by point-wise calculations and linear plot method and are also recorded in Table 1. The results show the stability order as Cu(II) > Zn(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II).

Since no co-ordinating group is present nearer the azo-group, the possibility of complexation will be least through its azo-nitrogen. The only possibility left is the co-ordination through 4-hydroxy and 5-carboxy groups. As such the dye will behave as a derivative of salicylic acid. Potentiometric titrations in different metal and ligand ratio indicated replacement of two protons per ligand molecule. This confirms, therefore, the co-ordination through 4-hydroxy and 5-carboxy groups of the salicylic residue. This is also in agreement with the results obtained by Drew and Fairbairn¹³ who had stated

that with the azo salicylic acids, co-ordination of metal with azo-nitrogen is not possible and that the metal is associated with the carboxy and hydroxy groups of the salicylic residue.

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References

1. WM. L. RUIGH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* : 1929, 51, 1456.
2. E. W. ENGEL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* : 1930, 52, 1812.
3. R. NORRIS SHERVE, M. W. SWANEY and E. H. RIECHERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1943, 65, 2241.
4. J. C. BAILAR and C. F. CALLIS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1952, 74, 6018.
5. C. F. CALLIS, N. C. NIELSEN and J. C. BAILAR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1952, 74, 3461.
6. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution, P. Haase and Son (Copenhagen,), 1941, p. 20.
7. H. M. LEWING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
8. P. V. KHADIKAR and R. L. AMERIA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 33.
9. P. V. KHADIKAR and S. N. KAKKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 1198.
10. P. V. KHADIKAR and R. L. AMERIA, *Indian J. Chem.* 1975, 13, 815.
11. D. POORNACHANDRA RAO and P. V. KHADIKAR, *Indian J. Chem.* (in press).
12. E. A. BRAUDE and F. C. NACHOD, "Determination of Organic Structure by Physical Methods", Academic Press, 1955, p. 567.
13. H. D. K. DREW and R. E. FAIRBAIRN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 823.